

QUIZ**LAST NAME:** Nidoh**FIRST NAME:** Soro**PROGRAM CODE:** DSDD**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **What is the first major step in writing a typical research paper?**
 - Define the research problem and analyze task.¹**
 - Select the research problem.
 - Write a preliminary outline.
 - Analyze data.
2. **What characterizes an excellent research paper?**
 - Use of many quotations.
 - Use of in-text citation.
 - Use of formal academic style, US or UK spelling, consistency and coherence and good referencing.²**

¹ EUCLID. *ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*. (Washington DC: Euclid University 2015), 2.

² EUCLID, 5–6.

Use of long quotations.

3. **What does research mean?**

It means to read interesting books and summarize them.

It means to find a research question and look for pertinent facts to answer it.³

It means to collect data from different sources.

It means to read and take notes systematically.

4. **What is the objective of researchers?**

To collect big data.

To convince readers of the soundness of a research question.

To find an answer to some bigger issue to help people understand a phenomenon.⁴

To publish articles in scientific journals.

5. **What are the most important sources of information for researchers?**

Secondary sources of information.

Primary sources of information.⁵

Tertiary sources of information.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 14.

⁴ Turabian, 15.

⁵ Turabian, 24–25.

Online sources of information.

6. **What is the importance of planning your research project?**

To work out your project quickly.

To assemble your argument in a coherent one.⁶

To monitor your progress.

To keep your records.

7. **What are the reasons for citing your sources?**

To tell reader that you are familiar with the author.

To challenge the existing body of knowledge.

To give credit or recognition to someone else work.⁷

To formulate a new social theory.

8. **What are the referencing styles in Turabian?**

Book-date style and title-bibliography style.

Author-time style and notes-citation style.

Title-date style and title-book style.

Author-date style and notes bibliography style.⁸

⁶ Turabian, 43–44.

⁷ Turabian, 86.

⁸ Turabian, 87.

9. **What challenges PhD students in the process of writing a qualitative dissertation?**

- Finding the right supervisor.
- Developing a good research proposal.
- Choosing and developing a researchable topic.⁹**
- Choosing a qualitative approach.

10. **What factors determines the choice of a qualitative research approach?**

- The ability to assess knowledge claim.
- The capacity to match the research approach to purposes, questions and issues.¹⁰**
- The ability of developing a deep understanding of a social setting.
- The ability of coining a new social theory.

⁹ Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008), 32.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, 33.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.